

HARSHACHARITA: THE FIRST HISTORICAL BIOGRAPHY IN SANSKRIT IN A FLORID & FANCIFUL STYLE

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ABSTRACTS:

In view of the antiquity and the developed character of Indian civilization it would indeed be ridiculous to expect to find India destitute of historical sense. But what is really essential is the fact that, despite the abundance of its literature, history is so miserably represented, and that in the whole of the great period of Sanskrit literature, there is not one writer who can be seriously regarded as a critical historian. One of the import stage in the development of Indian historiography started with Banabhatta in the first quarter of the 7th century A.D., when he wrote Harshacharita, a biography of his patron Pushyabhuti Harsha. It may be observed that Bana was a Bhargava and was inclined towards history by family tradition. His work Harshacharita is not merely a work of history, it is a literary work and belongs to the category of literature known as Kavya. In this work, Bana does not record the series of events as they happened and does not deal with the complete life of Harsha. Like other Kavya literature he tries to combine historical and factious stories and shows how Harsha attained the fortune. The central theme of his work is the attack on the Mukhari empire by a coalition of enemies, resulting in the death of the Mukhari emperor. Harsha marched with an army to drive out the enemies and recue his sister, who had escaped into the forests after the invasion. Bana provides to details of the war and ends narrative with the meeting of Harsha with Rajyasri. Thus Bana shows to his readers that Harsha legitimacy succeeded to the Empire.

KEY WORDS:

Antiquity, Civilization, Coalition, Destitute, Empire, Escaped, Historical, Invasion, Legitimacy ,Literature.

INVASION:

It is commonly held that before the dawn of the modern age India did not possess any historiography of any value and the study of Indian history was introduced by the foreigners. This impression seems to be ill-founded. While it cannot be denied that the people of India in the ancient times failed to write their history and did not produce many outstanding historians, it can not also be denied that there existed a vast amount of historical writings of various kinds. In “ An Introduction to Indian Historiography” Prof. Warder has not only made an investigation of the various historical writings, but also provides an outline to indicate that the Indian historiography possesses continuity from Vedic antiquity to modern times, but also asserts that “ what he has bough to light is probably a very limited selection from the extant historical writing in Indian languages, an unknown but possibly large number of texts remaining hidden in manuscript form”.¹

The deeds of Harsha (Harshacharita), is the biography of Indian emperor Harsha by Banabhatta, also known as Bana, who was a Sanskrit writer of Seventh Century CE India. He was the Asthana Kavi (Court Poet) of Harsha. The Harshacharita was the first composition of Bana and is considered to be the beginning of writing of historical poetic works in the Sanskrit Language. The Harshacharita ranks as the first historical biography in Sanskrit although it is written in a florid & fanciful style. Bana’s detailed and vivid descriptions of rural India’s natural environment as well as the extraordinary industry of the Indian people exudes the vitality of life at that time. Since he received the patronage of the patron are not an unbiased appraisal and presents the emperor’s actions in an overly favorable light. The Harshacharita, written in ornate poetic prose, narrates the biography of the emperor Harsha in eight Uchvasas (Chapters). In the first two chapters, Bana gives an account of his ancestry and his early life.²

A historical biography refers to the life, character and deeds of a historical personality, royal personage, eminent king, great ruler or emperor, who occupies an important place in the history of a particular nation or region. The ancestors of Harsha find mention in the third chapter of Harshacharita. In the words of Bana that, it was Pusyabhuti, who founded the Kingdom of Srikantha with its Capital at Thanesar. He has been described also as the founder of the royal Vardhana dynasty. His successors, Naravarshana, Rajyavardhana and Adityavardhana do not find place in the genealogy preserved in the work. These kings who flourished probably between 500 A.D and 580

A.D were the feudatory chiefs. They might have acknowledged the supremacy of the Guptas and the Maukharis. The next king in the line of Puspabhuti, as mentioned in the work was Prabhakarvardhana, who was blessed with two sons, Rajyavardhana and Harshavardhana and a daughter Rajyashri. Prabhakarvardhana (580-605 A.D) was an eminent and powerful king who assumed the titles Maharajadhiraja and Parambhattaraka. His wars and conquests have, been described in the fourth and fifth chapters.³

Banabhatta provides information that Prabhakarvardhana was “ A Lion to the Huna Deer”, a burning fever to the king of Sindhudesa, a troublers of the sleep of Gurjara King, a bilious plague to that scent-elephant, the Lord of Gandhara, a destroyer of the provide of the Latas, and an axe to the goddess fortune and glory of Malava”. In the fourth chapter itself it is stated that Rajyasri was married to Grahavarman, the son of the Maukhari Prince Avantivarman of Kanauj.⁴ The fifth chapter of Harshacharita is developed to Prabhakarvardhana and his eldest son Rajyavardhana’s conflicts with the Hunas. The former has been called” Hunaharinakeshari” because of his resounding victory over the Hunas . In order to strike another blow to the Hunas, Pravakarvardhana sent Rajyavardhana on a military expedition against them in the Uttarapatha. But before they could be finally subdued Rajyavardhan back to the capital on account of the illness of his father. His father had already expired and his mother had burnt herself to death on the bank of the Saraswati River.⁵

The ancient Indians had their own conception of a biographer history which need no comparison with that of ancient Greeks and Romans. Banabhatta mentioned in the sixth chapter that Rajyavardhana because of being socked and terribly upset offered the throne to his younger brother, Harsha. But Harsha was not willing to accept the throne and ultimately Rajyavardhana had to ascend the throne at Thaneswar (605 A.D). No sooner had Rajyavardhana ascended the throne, he received the sad news that the king of Malwa had attacked and killed Rajyasri and put her into the dungeon cell in Kanykubja. He chalked out a plan to attack also Thaneswar.⁶ However, Rajyavardhana in order to avenge the death of his brother-in- law and the humiliation of his sister at once marched with his troops for Malwa leaving his younger brother Harsha in capital. He had successfully ruled the Malwa Army and defeated king Devagupta but he was himself treacherously assassinated by the king of Gauda called Sasanka, who had came all the

way from his distant kingdom to assist his ally, king Devagupta of Malwa. This the coalition of common enemies of Rajyavardhan which has been perhaps called by Bana” Sasankamandali”. Having thus avenged the defeat of Devagupta of Malawa, the Gauda monarch Sasanka occupied Kanauj and released, the widowed Maukhari queen Rajyasri, from captivity in her own capital.⁷

Banabhatta has, maintained sequence and coherence to a considerable extent in the narration of events. Harsha was only sixteen years of age at a time when he heard the news of the tragic end of Rajyavardhana. He was reluctant to occupy then throne. But after being persuaded by the councilors of the state he agreed to take the reign in his hand, and ultimately ascended the throne of Thaneswar in 606 A.D. the immediate task before Harsha was to rescue his sister, who after having escaped from the prison had entered from the Vindhya forest and to relieve Kanauj from the control of Sasanka. When he was about to set out on his digvijay with a strong force, Hamsavega, a messenger of king Bhaskarvarman of Pragyo-tisa (Assam) entered his court with gifts & message of friendship. A perpetual treaty of friendship between these two contemporary kings was conducted as stated by Bana in the seventh chapter of his work.⁸

After the departure of Hamsavega from Thaneswar, Harsha entered the Vindhya forest and made a vigorous search for her sister, Rajyasri, and at last with the help of forest chiefs like Vyagraketu, Bhukampa and Nirghata and a Buddhist monk, Divakaramitra, rescued her at the moment when she was about to immolate herself. He along with his sister returned to his camp on the bank of the Ganga, as described in the seventh and eighth chapters of the work. In these two very chapters Banabhatta has described in detail the life and culture of the tribal people of the Vindhya region with special reference to the Sabaras. We are informed by Banabhatta that Harsha made an elaborate preparation to wage war against the Gauda king Sasanka, who is described as ‘ the vilest of Gaudas and the ‘ Vile Gauda Serpent’. But he does not provide us with any detail of the war between the two. It seems that the friendly alliance between Harsha of Thaneswar and Bhaskarvarman of Kamarupa struck fear in mind of Sasanka, and instead of facing an impending danger he withdraw from Kanauj which paved the way for Harsha to establish his rule there. He probably in the last phase of his life transferred his

capital from Thaneshwar to Kanauj and made it the seat of his power. Thus, he not only inherited the paternal kingdom but also got the Maukhari throne of Kanauj.⁹

The amalgamation of these two kingdoms helped him in consolidating his position and extending his authority and influence in all directions. Bana, while describing Harsha as a warrior and conqueror, informs us that he conquered Sindhudesa and annexed it to his kingdom of there by completed the unfinished task of his father. The river Indus formed the Western boundary of his empire. In the same chapter we are further informed that kings of the states in the Himalayan region were also subjugated by him. They after acknowledging his political supremacy started paying taxes to him. His conquest of Malwa and its annexation to his Kingdom finds mention in the seventh chapter of the author's work. Though we do not get a clear picture of the extent of Harsha's empire however, it is true that he earned name & fame as the last great Hindu emperor of North India.¹⁰

The biographies of many famous kings composed by their respective court poets provide us very useful data during the period. The information supplied by Bana in the second chapter of his work regarding the administrative system and military organization of Harsha is of considerable historical value. He has highlighted the feudal structure of his administration. Banabhatta has presented an enlarged picture of the feudal system that had already existed in ancient India prior to Harsha's time and in the time of Harsha. According to Bana, there were different categories of Samanta viz., Samanta, mahasamanta, aparsamanta, Pradhansamanta who offered their services to Harsha and his predecessors. The loyal and faithful Mahasamantas used to accompany the kings while going on military expedition. Some of the feudatory kings in the time of Harsha also find mention in the work. Bana has also focused on the inter-state relations in the time of Harsha. In the same chapter Bana has provided the details of military strength of the Harsha with special description of elephant force and cavalry.¹¹

The court historiographers not only enjoyed the royal patronage but also received the encouragement to record the history of their respective times which gradually led to the development of historical writing in ancient India. The information supplied by Bana in the second chapter of his work regarding the administrative system and military organization of Harsha is of considerable historical value. He has highlighted the feudal

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Bana himself had a number of companions from all strata of life which reveals that caste system and intermingling was not so strict. A long list of twenty seven kings of different dynasties that ruled over different kingdoms in ancient India furnished by Bana in the sixth chapter of his work on the basis of his knowledge of the past history also reserves our notice. Besides, information on education, dresses, ornaments of various kinds, forms of art, features of different race can be found in the Harshavardhana.¹⁴

No doubt, Harshacharita gives valuable information regarding the society, culture and other aspects of the period. Considered as the first of its kind, it served as an example to the later days poet. Bana has woven the story out of actual events' and his masterpiece' in fact is as much based on real events as Scott's *Quentin Durward* or *Waverlea*.¹⁵ It contains' a living India at that time, just as we see in Arrian and Plutarch something of the India of Alexander's time.

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